

Chemical Composition of *Myrtus communis* L. (Myrtaceae) Fruits

Karzan Omer Qader¹, Sahar A. A. Malik Al-Saadi^{2*} and Thuraya A. Al-Saadi³

¹Department of Biology, College of Science, Sulaimani University, Iraq.

²Department of Biology, College of Science, Basrah University, Iraq.

³Department of Science, College of Basic Education, Al-Mustansiriya University, Iraq.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Authors KOQ and SAAMAS designed the study, performed sample collection and processing and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Author TAAS wrote the protocol, managed the analyses of the study and managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

DOI: 10.9734/JALSI/2017/33746

Editor(s):

(1) Ali Mohamed Elshafei Ali, National Research Centre, Egypt.

Reviewers:

(1) Dildar Ahmed, Forman Christian College, Lahore, Pakistan.

(2) Aidi Wannas Wissem, Center of Biotechnology of the Technopol Borj-Cedria, Tunisia.

(3) Olabanji Iyabo Oluremi, Obafemi Awolowo University, Nigeria.

Complete Peer review History: <http://www.sciencedomain.org/review-history/19748>

Original Research Article

Received 27th April 2017
Accepted 17th June 2017
Published 28th June 2017

ABSTRACT

The chemical composition of *Myrtus communis* L. extracts were prepared and analyzed by GC-MS. Sixteen phytochemical constituents of chemical compounds were identified in fruits of *Myrtus communis*. The relative percentage of linoleic acid methyl ester was high (27.19%), followed by oleic acid methyl ester (21.18%) and then octane 3,5- dimethyl (16.47%), dodecane (11.39%), palmitic acid methyl ester (6.80%) and tetradecane (6.69%) as well as, some components present in lower percentage such as stearic acid methyl ester (3.32%).

Keywords: *Myrtus communis*; Myrtaceae; linoleic acid; GC-MS.

1. INTRODUCTION

Myrtle (*Myrtus communis* L.) is an aromatic evergreen perennial shrub or small tree

belonging to the Myrtaceae family that includes 130-140 genera and about 3000 - 4000 species growing in temperate, tropical and subtropical regions [1-3]. It is native plant in Mediterranean

*Corresponding author: E-mail: saharmalik2010@gmail.com;

region and Southern Europe. It grows wild in Africa, Europe and Asia including Turkey, Iraq, Iran and Syria [4-8]. *Myrtus communis* L. is an evergreen aromatic plant growing wild in Iraq and cultivated in gardens [9].

Common names for myrtle trees are "Yas" or "Habb Al-As", "Ace", "hambeles", "mersin" or "murt" [10-12]. Myrtle has upright stem, 1.8-3 m high with dark glossy green leaves that are opposite paired or whorled, glabrous, ovate to lanceolate with an entire margin. The flowers are fragrant and white or pinkish. The fruit is a round, reddish blue to violet berry [7,13-14].

Different parts of *Myrtus communis* fruits, leaves and branches have been used as a folk medicine for the treatment of various diseases. It is used as a stringent, antiseptic hemostatic, blood purifier, laxative, anti-diarrheal, hepatoprotective, analgesic, anti hemorrhagic and anti-hyperglycemic vaginal lavage, enemas or hair tonic with emetic effects and hypolipemic activities. It is also used to treat peptic ulcers, bleeding, headache, palpitation, leucorrhoea, urethritis, conjunctivitis, pulmonary, analgesic, anti hemorrhagic, wound healing skin diseases and respiratory diseases [1,15-40].

The activity of myrtle is likely explained by its chemical components such as alkaloids, tannins, phenol, flavonoids (quercetin, catechin and myricetin derivatives), sugars, organic acids (citric and malic acids), saponin, anthraquinones, essential oils, hydrocarbons, alcohols, anthocyanin pigments, esters and fatty acids [7,41-42]. The essential oil of myrtle has been studied by many researches [3,43-45]. The major components were linalool (28.28%), α -pinene, 1,8-cineole linalyl acetate, limonene and α -terpineol. Some researchers have shown that the main components were 1,8-cineole (26.55%), α -pinene (19.40%), linalool (15.97%), terpineol and linalyl acetate [12,37,46-49].

The fatty acid content in the fruits of myrtle have been described previously [24,39,50-54]. Serce et al. [55] studied antioxidant activities of fatty acid composition of *Myrtus communis*, and reported that oleic acid is the dominant fatty acid (67.07%) followed by palmitic acid (10.24%) and stearic acid (8.19%), respectively.

The aims of this paper are to determine some chemical components of pickling herbs and *Myrtus communis* L. fruits using GC-MS.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Plant Material

Myrtus communis L. fruits were collected from the north of Iraq and air dried. The powdered fruits (150 g) were extracted using 500 mL of n-hexane via a Soxhlet apparatus for 48 hours. The extracts were concentrated with a rotary evaporator.

2.2 Gas Chromatography-MS Analysis

GC-MS analysis was carried out in University of Basrah, College of Agriculture, Iraq using a Shimadzu GC-QP 2010 ultra-gas chromatograph. The GC oven temperature was programmed from 40°C to 280°C at a rate of 15°C/min. Helium was used as a carrier gas. The inlet pressure was 96.1 kPa. The linear velocity was 47.2 cm/sec. The column flow was 1.71 mL/min, and the injector temperature was 280°C with split injection mode. The MS scan conditions included the following: source temperature, 200°C; interface temperature, 280°C; detector gain, 0.69 kV +0.10 kV; scan speed, 1666; range 50 m/z to, 800 m/z. The components of the *Myrtus communis* were identified by comparing the spectra with known compounds stored in the NIST library (2005).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The GC-MS chromatogram of *Myrtus communis* fruit extract (Fig. 1; Table1) showed sixteen peaks indicating the presence of sixteen compounds (phytochemical constituents). The identification of the phytochemical compounds was confirmed based on the molecular formula, peak area and retention time.

Most of the chemical components from *Myrtus communis* fruits are fatty acid methyl ester 4-5 components including linoleic acid methyl ester (27.19%), oleic acid methyl ester (21.18%), octane, 3,5-dimethyl was (16.47%) and dodecane (11.39%), palmitic acid methyl ester (6.80%), tetradecane (6.69%), and stearic acid methyl ester (3.32%) (Table 1; Fig. 1). Our results agreed with the literature [7,55] and identified palmitic acid, oleic acid and stearic acid. There were less fatty acids than the literature. Serce et al. [55] reported that the main fatty acids in the fruits of myrtle were oleic acid (62.13%) and palmitic acid. This was confirmed in our data.

In this study, the order of fatty acid methyl esters is as follows linoleic > oleic>. The results agree also with Serce et al. [55] who also found nonadecanoic acid methyl ester, eicosane, heneicosane. Our data conflict with Cakir, 2004. They reported lauric and myristic acids, but these were not detected in this study. Furthermore, there is an association between fruit color and fatty acid composition in myrtle plants. Darker fruits contain more fatty acids than white-fruits [55].

Many researchers reported that the chemical compounds found in medicinal plants change as a function of region. This may be due to genetic and environmental factors. The presence and absence of constituents can impact, the formation and genesis of products in the plants. Environmental factors such as climate, irrigation, soil, harvest season, temperature range, method of drying, storage conditions, and even the part of the plant tissue evaluated are all parameters that should be considered [14,56].

Fig. 1. Chromatogram of chemical compounds of *Myrtus communis* fruits

Table 1. Chemical compounds of *Myrtus communis* L. fruits using gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS)

Peak	M.F.	R. Time	Area	Area%	Component
1	C ₁₀ H ₂₂	8.099	10294381	16.47	Octane, 3,5-dimethyl
2	C ₁₂ H ₂₆	11.215	307237	0.49	2,6-Dimethyldecane
3	C ₁₂ H ₂₆	12.000	7120713	11.39	Dodecane
4	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	14.999	4184900	6.69	Tetradecane
5	C ₁₇ H ₃₆	17.592	1443503	2.31	Heptadecane
6	C ₂₀ H ₄₂	20.051	475506	0.76	Eicosane
7	C ₁₇ H ₃₄ O ₂	21.545	4253483	6.80	Palmitic acid methyl ester
8	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O ₂	22.276	310572	0.50	Nonadecanoic acid methyl ester.
9	C ₁₉ H ₃₄ O ₂	23.097	16999092	27.19	Linoleic acid methyl ester
10	C ₁₉ H ₃₆ O ₂	23.152	13242185	21.18	Oleic acid, methyl ester
11	C ₁₉ H ₃₈ O ₂	23.356	2078401	3.32	Stearic acid, methyl ester
12	C ₁₂ H ₄₄	23.910	251860	0.40	Heneicosane
13	C ₁₃ H ₂₄ O ₂	24.459	282957	0.45	Tridecanedial
14	C ₂₁ H ₄₂ O ₂	24.797	284763	0.46	Methyl 18-methylnonadecanoate
15	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄	26.051	599020	0.96	1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, diisooctyl ester
16	C ₃₆ H ₇₄	27.979	379950	0.61	Hexatriacontane
			62508523	100.00	

Myrtle fruits are used as food and they contain high vitamin contents and volatile oils that can offer several pharmacological effects and are used in the food and cosmetic industries [57-61].

The major essential fatty acid (linolenic acid methyl ester) is an antioxidant that can protect membranes from harm. It also inhibits proliferation of ER-positive and ER- negative breast cancer cells [62]. *Myrtus communis* contains many essential oils, tannins, terpenes, phenolic acids, hydrocarbons, alcohols, anthocyanin pigments, esters and fatty acids [62]. This can have anti-inflammatory, cancer preventive, hypocholesterolemic, hepato protective, antihistaminic, anti-androgenic, anti-arthritis, nematicide and insecticide properties as well as heart-protecting properties [10,63-68]. *M. communis* extracts exhibit antibacterial, anti-parasite, anti-fungal, antiviral, and nematicidal activities and counteract infectious diseases [41,69-75].

4. CONCLUSION

GC-MS analysis revealed that 16 different chemical components were identified in the *Myrtus communis*, with high amount of linoleic acid (27.19%) helpful in revealing the pharmaceutical value of the plant. it also provides information about its trado-medical use. GC-MS analysis is important step towards understanding the nature of active ingredients in this medicinal plant and mentioned

phytocompounds would be useful in the preparation of novel drugs for treating diseases.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

- Romani A, Pinelli P, Mulinacci N, Vincieri FF, Tattini M. Identification and quantification of polyphenols in leaves of *Myrtus communis*. *Chromatographia*. 1999;49(2):17-20.
- Ghannadi A, Dezfuly N. Essential oil analysis of the leaves of Persian true Myrtle. *Int. J. Med. Arom. Plants*. 2011;1(2):48-50.
- Al-Edany TY, Al-Saadi SA. Taxonomic significance of anatomical characters in some species of the family Myrtaceae. *American Journal of Plant Sciences*. 2012;3:572-581.
- Nadkarni KM. *Indian Materia Medica*, 3rd Edn, Popular Prakashan Pvt. Ltd., Bombay. 1989;1:838.
- Barboni TM, Cannac L, Massi Y, Ramirez P, Chiaramonti N. Variability of polyphenol compounds in *Myrtus communis* L. (Myrtaceae) berries from Corsica. *Molecules*. 2010;15(11):7849-7860.

6. Hassiotis CN, Lazari DM. Decomposition process in the Mediterranean region. Chemical compounds and essential oil. International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation; 2010;64(5):356-362.
7. Sumbul S, Ahmed MA, Asif M, Akhtar M. *Myrtus communis* Linn. -a review. Indian J Nat Prod Resour. 2011;2:395-402.
8. Aleksic V, Knezevic P. Antimicrobial and antioxidative activity of extracts and essential oils of *Myrtus communis* L. Microbiol Res. 2013;168(6):311-332.
9. Pezhmanmehr M, Dastan D, Erahimi SN, Hadian J. Essential oil constituents of leaves and fruits of *Myrtus communis* L. from Iran. Journal of Essential Oil-Bearing Plants; 2009.
10. Baytop T. Treatment with plants in Turkey. İstanbul: İstanbul Univ Publ. 1984; 3255.
11. Özcan M, Chalchat JC. Effect of collection period on the flavour profiles of the leaves of myrtle tree (*Myrtus communis* L.) growing wild in Turkey. Res. J. Chem. Environ. 2004;8(1):70-73.
12. AL-Hadeethi MA, AL- Anbari AK, AL-Dulimi SA. Identify the essential oils in *Myrtus Communis* L. Leaves. Int'l Journal of Advances in Chemical Engg & Biological Sciences (IJACEBS). 2015;2(2): 116-118.
13. Rechinger KH. Flora Iranica. Akademische Druck and Verlagsanstalt, Graz, Austria; 1982.
14. Bouaziz A, khennouf S, Abu zarga M, Abdalla S, Baghiani A, Charef N. Phytochemical analysis, hypotensive effect and antioxidant properties of *Myrtus communis* L. growing in Algeria. Asian Pac. J. Trop. Biomed. 2015;5(1):19-28.
15. Kirtikar KR, Basu BD. Indian medicinal plants, 3rd Edn. International Book Distributors, Dehra Dun. 1988;2:1040-1042.
16. Ali M, Ansari SH. Herbal drugs used as hair tonic. In: National seminar on the use of traditional medicinal plants in skincare, CIMAP, Lucknow. 1994;20.
17. Maccioni S, Tomei PE, Rizzo A. The medicinal use of wild and cultivated plant species in the folk tradition of the Val di Magra. Memoirs of the Academy of Sciences Lunigianese. 1995;389-435.
18. Baytop T. Therapy with medicinal plants in Turkey (Past and Present). Nobel Tip Kitapevleri Press, İstanbul; 1999.
19. Martin T, Rubio B, Villaescua L, Fernandez L, Diaz AM. Polyphenolic compounds from pericarps of *Myrtus communis*. Pharm. Biol. 1999;37:28-31.
20. Özek T, Demirci B, Baser KHC. Chemical composition of Turkish myrtle oil. J. Essent. Oil Res. 2000;12:541-544.
21. Savikin-Fodulovic KP, Bulatovic VM, Menkovic NR, Grubisic DV. Comparison between the essential oil of *Myrtus communis* L. obtained from naturally grown and *in vitro* plants. Journal of Essential Oil Research. 2000;12:75-78.
22. Koukos PK, Papadopoulou KI, Papagiannopoulos AD, Patiaka DTh. Chemicals from Greek forestry biomass-constituents of the leaf oil of *Myrtus communis* L. grown in Greece. Journal of Essential Oil Research. 2001;13:245-246.
23. Azadbakht M. Myrtle, In: Iranian herbal pharmacopoeia editorial committee (Eds.), Iranian Herbal Pharmacopoeia. Publications of Ministry of Health, Tehran. 2002;747-753.
24. Cakir A. Essential oil and fatty acid composition of the fruits of *Hippophae rhamnoides* L. and *Myrtus communis* L. from Turkey. Biochem. Syst. Ecol. 2004;32:809-816.
25. Romani A, Coinu R, Carta S, Pinelli P, Galardi C, Vincieri FF, Franconi F. Evaluation of antioxidant effect of different extracts of *Myrtus communis* L. Free Radic. Res. Jan. 2004;38(1):97-103.
26. Trease W, Evans D. Pharmacognosy, 15th Edn, W.B. Saunders Comp Ltd. Toronto. 2006;477.
27. Coruh N, Sagdcoglucelep A, Ozgokce F, Iscan M. Antioxidant capacities of *Gundelia tourefortii* L. extracts and inhibition on glutathione-S-transferase activity. Food Chemistry. 2007;100(3):1249-1253.
28. Alamanni MC, Cossu M. Radical scavenging activity and antioxidant activity of liquors of myrtle (*Myrtus communis* L.) berries and leaves, Ital. J. Food Sci. 2007;16:197-208.
29. Chryssavgi G, Papageorgiou Vassiliki, Mallouchos Athanasios, Theodosis Kibouris, Komaitis Michael. Essential oil composition of *Pistacia lentiscus* L. and *Myrtus communis* L. Evaluation of antioxidant capacity of methanolic extracts. Food Chemistry. 2008;107:1120-1130.
30. Bugarin D. Antioxidant, antimicrobial and antimutagenic potential of the *Myrtus*

- communis* L. PhD dissertation, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad; 2010.
31. Mahboubi M, Ghazian N, Bidgoli F. *In vitro* synergistic efficacy of combination of amphotericin B with *Myrtus communis* essential oil against isolates of *Candida albicans*. *Phytomedicine*. 2010;17:771-774.
 32. Tuberoso CIG, Rosa A, Bifulco E, Melis MP, Atzeri A, Pirisi FM, Desse MA. Chemical composition and antioxidant activities of *Myrtus communis* L. berries extracts. *Food Chem*. 2010;123:1242–1251.
 33. Hosseinzadeh H, Khoshdel M, Ghorbani, M. Antinociceptive, anti-inflammatory effects and acute toxicity of aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Myrtus communis* L. aerial parts in mice. *J. Acupunct Meridian Stud*. 2011;4:242-247.
 34. Haghi G, Hatami A, Arshi R. Distribution of caffeic acid derivatives in *Gundelia tournefortii* L. *Food Chemistry*. 2011;124: 1029–1035.
 35. Oryan S, Nasri S, Amin GR, Kazemi-Mohammady SMM, Shahrekord J. Anti nociceptive and anti-inflammatory effects of aerial parts of *Gundelia tournefortii* L. on NMRI male mice. *J. Shahrekord. Univ. Med. Sci*. 2011;12:8-15.
 36. Tumen I, Senol FS, Orhan IE. Inhibitory potential of the leaves and berries of *Myrtus communis* L. (myrtle) against enzymes linked to neurodegenerative diseases and their antioxidant actions. *Int. J. Food Sci. Nutr*. 2012;63:387-392.
 37. Ardakani AS, Hosyninejad SA, Pourshirzad A. Killing effects of *Myrtus communis* L. essential oil on *Meloidogyne incognita*. *Research article. Intl. J. Agri. Crop Sci*. 2013;5(8):806-810.
 38. Alipour G, Dashti S, Hosseinzadeh H. Review of pharmacological effects of *Myrtus communis* L. and its active constituents. *Phytother. Res.*, 2014;28: 1125-1136.
 39. Melito S, La Bella S, Martinelli F, Cammalleri L, Tuttolomondo T, Leto C, Fadda A, Molinu MG, Mulas M. Morphological, chemical, and genetic diversity of wild myrtle (*Myrtus communis* L.) populations in Sicily. *Turk. J. Agric. For*. 2016;40:249-261.
 40. Meriem T. Chemical composition and anti-inflammatory activity of *Myrtus communis* L. essential oil. *Algerian Journal of Arid Environment*. 2016;6(2):73-82.
 41. Sarkarti A, Salamat M. Effect of moored on H.B.V and negativity of positive antigene. *Shiraz. First Symp. of Med. Ind*. 1997;134-135.
 42. Farhang HR, Vahabi MR, Allafchian AR. Chemical compositions of the essential oil of *Gundelia tournefortii* L. (Asteraceae) from Central Zagros, Iran. *Journal of Herbal Drugs*. 2016;6(4):227-233.
 43. Chalchat JC, Figueredo G, Özcan MM, Unver A. Effects on chemical compositions of essential oil of pickling herb and myrtle plants South West. *J. Hortic. Biol. Environ*. 2010;1(2):133-141.
 44. Akin M, Aktumsek A, Nostro A. Antibacterial activity and composition of the essential oils of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* Dehn and *Myrtus communis* L. growing in Northern Cyprus. *Afr. J. Biotechnol*. 2010;9(4):531-535.
 45. Siadat S, Direkvand-Moghadam F, Poshtdar A. Phytochemical of constituents of essential oil from *Myrtus communis* L. by GC-MS analysis. *Advanced Herbal Medicine*. 2016;2(3):33-38.
 46. Bouzabata A, Boussaha F, Casanova J. Tomi F. Composition and chemical variability of leaf oil of *Myrtus communis* from north-eastern Algeria. *Natural Product Communications*. 2010;5(10) :1659-1662.
 47. Snoussi A, Kachouri F, Chaabouni MM, Bouzouita N. Comparative GC analyses of ripe fruits, leaves and floral buds essential oils of Tunisian *Myrtus communis* L. *Mediterranean Journal of Chemistry*. 2011;1(1):38-43.
 48. Ghnaya AB, Chograni H, Messoud C, Boussaid M. Comparative chemical composition and antibacterial activities of *Myrtus Communis* L. essential oils isolated from Tunisian and Algerian Population. *Journal of Plant Pathology And Microbiology*. 2013;4(7):1-5.
 49. Benchikh F, Benabdallah H, Dahamna S, Khennouf S, Flamini G, Amira S. Antimotility and andidiarrhoeal activity of *Myrtus communis* L. leaves essential oil in mice. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016;8(7):1238-1244.
 50. Aidi Wannes W, Mhamdi B, Marzouk B. Variations in essential oil and fatty acid

- composition during *Myrtus communis* var. *italica* fruit maturation. Food Chemistry. 2009;112:621–626.
51. Aidi Wannas W, Mhamdi Sriti B, Ben Jemia M, Ouchikh O, Hamdaoui G, Kchouk ME, Marzouk B. Antioxidant activities of the essential oils and methanol extracts from myrtle (*Myrtus communis* var. *italica* L.) leaf, stem and flower. Food and Chemical Toxicology. 2010;48:1362–1370.
 52. Aidi Wannas W, Mhamdi B, Sriti J, Marzouk B. Glycerolipid and fatty acid distribution in pericarp, seed and whole fruit oils of *Myrtus communis* var. *italica*. Industrial Crops and Products. 2010;31: 77–83.
 53. Messaoud C, Boussaid M. *Myrtus communis* berry color morphs: A comparative analysis of essential oils, fatty acids, phenolic compounds, and antioxidant activities. Chemistry & Biodiversity. 2011;8(2):300-310.
 54. Al-Hajjar MA, Al-Shahiry KF, Al-Abache, SM. Isolation and identification of some active constituents of *Myrtus Communis* in Iraq by using HPLC, FT-IR techniques. Iraqi National Journal of Chemistry. 2012;45:11-22.
 55. Serce S, Ercisli S, Sengul M, Gunduz K, Orhan E. Antioxidant activities and fatty acid composition of wild grown myrtle (*Myrtus communis* L.) fruits. Phcog. Mag. 2010;6:9-12.
 56. Skotti E, Anastasaki E, Kanellou G, Polissiou M, Tarantilis PA. Total phenolic content, antioxidant activity and toxicity of aqueous extracts from selected Greek medicinal and aromatic plants. Ind. Crops Prod. 2014;53:46-54.
 57. Chalchat J, Garry RP, Michet A. Essential oils of myrtle of the Mediterranean littoral, J. Essent. Oil Res. 1998;10:613-617.
 58. Issa AY, Volate SR, Wargovich MJ. The role of phytochemicals in inhibition of cancer and inflammation: New directions and perspectives. J. Food Compos. Anal. 2006;19:405-419.
 59. Mimica-Dukić N, Bugarin D, Grbović S, Mitić-Ćulafić D, Vuković-Gačić B, Orčić D, Jovin E, Couladis M. Essential oil of *Myrtus communis* L. as a potential antioxidant and antimutagenic agents. Molecules. 2010;15: 2759-2770.
 60. Kanoun K, Belyagoubi-Benhammou N, Ghembaza N, Atik Bekkara F. Comparative studies on antioxidant activities of extracts from the leaf, stem and berry of *Myrtus communis* L. International Food Research Journal 2014;21(5):1957-1962.
 61. Bettaiebi A, Moujahedi N, Hamdaoui G, Ksouri R. Secondary compounds characterization of five aromatic plants growing wild in Tunisia. 2016;28(6):1596-1601.
 62. Yi Ha PM, Storkson M, Pariza W. Inhibition of benzo (a) pyreneinduced mouse forestomach neoplasia by conjugated dienoic derivatives of linoleic acid. Cancer Res. 1990;50:1097-1101.
 63. Karamanoğlu K. Pharmaceutic botanic. Ankara: Ankara Univ. Ecz. Fak. Yay; 1972.
 64. Mazza G. Gas chromatographic-mass spectrometric investigation of the volatile components of myrtle berries (*Myrtus communis* L.). J. Chromatogr. 1983;264:304-311.
 65. Duke JA. Handbook of medicinal herbs. Boca: CRC. 1988;198–199.
 66. Mulas M, Melis R. Essential oil composition of myrtle (*Myrtus communis*) leaves. J. Herbs Spices Med. Plants. 2011;17(1):21-34.
 67. Takaishi M, Fujita F, Uchida K, Yamamoto S, Sawada M, Hatai C. 1, 8-cineole, a TRPM8 agonist, is a novel natural antagonist of human TRP. Mol. Pain. 2012;8(1):86-87.
 68. Pérez-Rosés R, Risco E, Vila R, Penalver P, Cañigueral S. "Antioxidant activity of eleven essential oils by two different *In Vitro* Assays". 39th International Symposium of Essential Oils. Germany. 2008;39- 47.
 69. Agarwal VS. Economic plants of India. Kailash Prakashan, Calcutta. 1986;251.
 70. Mansouri S. Inhibition of *Staphylococcus aureus* mediated by extracts from Iranian plants. Pharm. Biol. 1999;5:375–377.
 71. Mansouri S, Foroumadi A, Ghaneie T, Najar AG. Antibacterial activity of the crude extracts and fractionated constituents of *Myrtus communis*, Pharm. Biol. 2001;39: 399–401.
 72. Keyhanfara M, Nazerib S, Bayatb M. Evaluation of antibacterial activities of some medicinal plants, traditionally used in Iran. Iranian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Winter. 2011;8(1):353-358.

73. Taheri A, Seyfan A, Jalalinezhad S, Naser F. Antibacterial effect of *Myrtus communis* hydro-alcoholic extract on pathogenic bacteria. Zahedan J. Res. Med. Sci. 2013;15(6):19-24.
74. Ghnaya AB, Chograni H, Messoud C, Boussaid M. Comparative chemical composition and antibacterial activities of *Myrtus communis* L. Essential oils isolated from Tunisian and Algerian population. J. Plant Pathol. Microb. 2013;4:186.
75. Mahmoudvand H, Ezzatkah F, Sharififar F, Sharifi I, Dezaki ES. Antileishmanial and cytotoxic effects of essential oil and methanolic extract of *Myrtus communis* L. Korean J. Parasitol. 2015;53(1):21-27.

© 2017 Qader et al.; This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Peer-review history:

The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:
<http://sciencedomain.org/review-history/19748>